

“HIGH FIDELITY MOCK-UP ON INVISION”

DELIVERABLE
D2.4

Version 2.1
07 2024

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Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUStry-Academia
Collaborations

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Date	Comments	Version
31/05/2023	<i>Version 1 Submitted in May 2023</i>	V1.0
28/05/2024	<i>Final Version</i>	V2.0
17/07/2024	<i>Final version resubmitted to Participant Portal following General Project Review Consolidated Report</i>	V2.1

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centered co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop of solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalized nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centered design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students, and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial, and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This report D2.4: “High fidelity mock-up on Invision” is part of Work Package (WP) 2: “Platform set up” of the project “Quick Challenge-driven, Human Centered Co-creation Mechanism for Industry-Academia Collaborations” (INDUSAC).

The goal of this deliverable is to graphically represent the users’ journey for Students, Researchers, and Companies as defined in WP1 (Human-centered development of the INDUSAC co-creation methodology) and described in D1.3 (User Journey Maps and user guidance), including the nine Predefined Collaborative Approaches (PCAs) templates and the corresponding Challenge templates for companies to post as defined in D1.2 (Predefined Collaborative Approaches).

This report also includes a visual representation of the platform’s administration functionalities that will allow the INDUSAC team to control, monitor, and manage all flows related to users (Registration, Profiles, Communication activities), content (Challenges, Letters of Motivation, Solutions and Evaluations scorecards) and efficiently deploy the defined INDUSAC methodology so that all processes are well aligned with the functionalities that the Platform has to provide.

The Platform High Fidelity Wireframe is built in Figma (access via the Figma Indusac Project link), where it includes (1) the new sections and templates (PCAs) as defined in the phases (Planning Phase, Onboarding Phase, Search Phase, Project Phase, and Offboarding Phase) and described in the deliverables D1.2 and D1.3, and (2) the Platform Administration functionalities.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Dx.x	Deliverable
INDUSAC	Quick challenge-driven, human-centered co-creation
mechanism for INDUSty-ACademia collaborations	
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
WP	Work Package
PCA	Predefined Collaborative Approach
INDUSAC Evaluation team	INDUSAC Evaluation Board and Company
representative	
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

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I. INTRODUCTION

Based on the baseline report, the methodology has been enhanced to provide comprehensive user journey maps for students, researchers, and companies. In addition, the methodology includes detailed guidance packages to facilitate the INDUSAC co-creation process.

According to the WP1 description from the INDUSAC Grant Agreement, user journey maps were developed for the main stakeholders of the INDUSAC platform, including companies and students/researchers. These maps are translated into a visual funnel for users' objectives during the different phases of the methodology that occur within the INDUSAC Community Platform. The two guidance packages developed based on these maps guide the back-office definition for INDUSAC team platform management, including process definition, management guidelines, and other relevant items. A visual representation of the INDUSAC team Management dashboards is also provided in this report.

The baseline report established a foundation by identifying current user interaction patterns and areas for improvement. Building on this, the enhanced methodology offers structured user journey maps to optimize experiences and meet stakeholder goals. These maps outline each user's path from initial engagement to objective completion, highlighting critical touchpoints and potential challenges.

The guidance packages provide the INDUSAC team with step-by-step instructions for platform management, ensuring an efficient and cohesive environment. Additionally, visual representations of the management dashboards offer an overview of operational metrics and performance indicators, supporting effective platform oversight.

II. PHASES

The report shows graphic representations, templates, dashboards, and users' profiles in relation to the INDUSAC methodology that take place within the Platform. Considering the five phases defined in WP1, the Platform provides support as follows:

1. Planning Phase

The [INDUSAC](https://indusac.eu) (Figure 1) main website connects to the [INDUSAC Community platform](#) (Figure 2) via a series of links under “Join Now!” section, and the listed challenges posted by companies (Figure 3).

Companies can also access the Platform from the registration and by accepting invitations sent by INDUSAC team members (Figure 4).

Figure 1 : INDUSAC main website: [https://indusac.eu/](https://indusac.eu) 13/05/2024

Figure 2 : INDUSAC Community Platform link. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

Search of technology offers...

PCAs

Organisation

Country

Industry

Clear

Showing 1 to 15 of 54 results

<p>New Improved Plant Protein Upcycled from Rice Brokens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative Products and Technologies Netherlands <p>Read More Collaborate</p>			
<p>A New Pepper Seeds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative Products and Technologies Yissum - Research Development Company of the Hebrew University Israel <p>Read More Collaborate</p>			

Figure 3 : Listed challenges posted by Companies.
<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/challenges>. 13/05/2024

Membership Invites Management

Pending Membership Invites Accepted Membership Invites

Email Address	Invite Date	Status	Actions
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage
[Redacted]	15/09/2022	Pending	Manage

Showing 1 to 7 of 7 entries

Figure 4 : The INDUSAC team invites companies to join from the Administration Dashboard. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

2. Onboarding Phase

The onboarding phase is designed to streamline the process for companies to register on the platform and access PCA (Pre-defined Collaboration Approaches) templates, enabling them to effectively describe and post their Challenges. The first step for companies is to sign up on the platform, providing essential information as shown in (Figure 5).

Once registered, companies can issue Challenges that students and researchers can address through Motivation Letters and Solution Proposals. Each Challenge will be guided by one of the nine PCAs, each targeting a distinct area such as developing a robust product, conducting market analysis, or creating a business model.

More information about PCAs can be found in the ANNEXES (Page 39).

(This figure belongs to Figure 5)

Sign Up to INDUSAC

Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for industry-academia collaborations

Name of the company *

Address of the company *

Country *

Number of employees *

List of NACE Codes *

Name of legal representative *

VAT number *

ID number *

(This figure belongs to Figure 5)

Web page *

Name of contact person *

Email of contact person *

Password for the new account *

Enter the characters from the image *

I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.*

we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Companies.*

I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (company data, such as specific contacts, to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published.*

Create an account

Figure 5 : Company registration form. <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/request-access> - 13/05/2024

Upon registration completion and once Terms and Conditions have been confirmed, the Company will set up their organization and their company representative profiles within the platform (Figures 6 and 7). Each company representative accepts the Terms and conditions.

The screenshot shows the user interface of the Indusac platform. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for Home, My Activity, My Network, Messages, Notifications, Management, and Resources. A search bar is located on the left. The main content area displays the profile of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya, Hungary. The profile includes a header with the company logo and name, a 'More...' button, and a description: 'Small and Medium Enterprise · Hungary · 0 followers'. Below the header, there are several sections: 'Opportunities (1)' with sub-sections for About, Jobs, Members (1), and Events; 'Latest Open Innovation Opportunities' featuring an 'Innovation Needs (1)' card; and 'RELATED PROFILES' with a profile for Sarolta Biró (0 followers) and a 'Follow' button. A 'View more profiles' link is also present. At the bottom right, there are links for 'InnogetCloud's Terms of Use' and 'Cookies Policy', and a copyright notice: '© 2023 InnogetCloud'. A large, faint gear graphic is overlaid on the bottom half of the page.

Figure 6 : Company Profile (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

Figure 7 : Company Representative Profile. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

The company will then have access to the nine PCA templates as defined in D1.2. A graphic representation of the PCA is available in Figure 8. The Company will complete the Challenge description based on the guidance provided for each PCA and submit it for the INDUSAC team to review.

(This figure belongs to Figure 8)

Home
My Activity
My Network
Messages
Notifications
Resources

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario/Trend analysis and references (e.g., Word)
- Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g., Excel)

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2..)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here
Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:
What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Publish

Save Draft

Manage posts

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Type in a search term

- Aerospace • Agriculture and Marine Resources • Agrofood Industry • Biological Sciences • Communications •
- Computer related • Consumer related • Digitalization • Electronics Related Market • Electronics, IT and Telecomms •
- Energy Market • Energy Technology • Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology • Industrial Products • Industrial Technologies •
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies • Lightweight • Measurements and Standards • Medical Health related •
- Ophthalmology • Other • Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences • Protecting Man and Environment • Social and Economics concerns •
- Sustainability •

Input:

Do you have scenarios/already known trends available to give to students?

Write your answer

Minimum 150 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Link to Slack-Channel:

Insert Link

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

Click to select a challenge manager among your company account subusers

INDUSAC Submission agreement

Users who want to submit a proposal to your challenge will carefully read the terms of the agreement and will send the form only if they agree and accept the conditions you include in the INDUSAC Submission Agreement. Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set in order to specify the cooperation. Additional agreements are subordinantes of the INDUSAC submission agreement. If there is a conflict, INDUSAC submission agreement prevails.

[View the Submission Agreement provided by INDUSAC](#)

I agree to use this submission agreement Create my own submission agreement

Privacy settings for this challenge

Post as Taras Zaiachuk from Company Post as Company

Figure 8 : PCA1 - Customer Needs (and Product properties) of tomorrow. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

Please note that PCA1 serves as the example, you can review the full list of 9 PCAs in IV.ANNEXES part of this document

A content management dashboard (Figure 9) is designed for INDUSAC team members to review, approve, or reject Challenges submitted by companies before publicly posting them for students and researchers to apply to.

Management Of Challenges (PCAs)

Challenges ↓

Approvals queue | **Posted Challenges** | Challenge to be modified | Challenge Rejected | Modified challenges

Show 10 entries Search:

Id	Status	Title	Posted on	Sent by	Managed by	Deadline	Actions
37	Deadline completed	Digital Online platform - Test for workshop	2023-11-17	Elene Bokeria Company Elene Bokeria Company	Manqi Qiu	2024-02-16	See challenge Delegate Delete Extend deadline
38	Deadline completed	Digital Online platform - Test for workshop 2		Elene Bokeria Company Elene Bokeria Company	Manqi Qiu	2024-02-16	See challenge Delegate Delete Extend deadline
39	Posted	HerbieIoT	2023-11-22	Scepter d.o.o., Milan Zajc Scepter d.o.o., Milan Zajc	Dusko Odic	2024-05-30	See challenge Delegate Delete Extend deadline
40	Posted	Re-thought of	2023-	Gábor	Szabina	2024-05-	See challenge

Figure 9 : Challenge Management dashboard for INDUSAC team to review Company Challenges (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

The Challenge can be either approved or rejected by the INDUSAC team. If the Challenge is rejected the Company is notified via an email and the Company can go to their content management dashboard (Figure 9) to edit the Challenge again and re-submit.

The dashboard features a search bar at the top with the text "Find a publication by title or ID" and a "+ Add new" button. Below the search bar, there is a "Filter by date" button. The main content area displays a list of challenges under the heading "MAY 2023 (3)". Each challenge entry includes a title, a description, and a set of statistics: "New contacts", "Rejected contacts", "Contacted contacts", and "Evaluated contacts". Each entry also has an "Editing" button and a "Manage" button with a dropdown arrow. The left sidebar contains filters for "View By Type" (All (3), Innovation Needs (3), Technology Offers (0)) and "View By Status" (All (3), Editing (3), Submitted (0), Active (0), Archived (0)).

Figure 10 : Dashboard for Company Challenge Management. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

In case the Challenge is approved, the company gets a notification email and it will be publicly posted for students and researchers to apply to, so it will enter into the Search Phase which includes the students/researchers' signup process into the Platform, and student/researcher teams' application through the Motivation Letter.

3. Search Phase

Similarly to the Company Onboarding phase, students and researchers will be able to access the INDUSAC Community platform to participate in the application process, submit their Motivation Letters as a co-creation team, and proceed to co-develop solutions with the Company - if selected.

The [INDUSAC](http://www.indusac.eu) (Figure 11) main website connects to the [INDUSAC Community platform](#) (Figure 12) via a series of links under "Join Now!" section, and the listed challenges posted by companies (Figure 13).

Figure 11 : INDUSAC main website <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/> 13/05/2024

Figure 12 : INDUSAC Community platform. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 13/05/2024

Showing 1 to 15 of 54 results

<p>New Improved Plant Protein Upcycled from Rice Broken</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative Products and Technologies Netherlands <p>Read More Collaborate</p>			
<p>A New Pepper Seeds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative Products and Technologies Yissum - Research Development Company of the Hebrew University Israel <p>Read More Collaborate</p>			

Figure 13 : INDUSAC Community Platform link <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/challenges> - 13/05/2024

Students and researchers can filter (Figure 14) according to their preferred PCA and Challenge topic/ type, Country of the Company, Company Sector, and active and inactive challenges and there will be a search engine to type in by keywords and get full access to the description of each of the Challenges (Figure 15). They can initiate the registration process from the Challenge description page as well.

Search...

Challenge Type Organization Country Industry Clear

Showing 1 to 15 of 114 results

Selection of the equipment to support system for digitization of entire, natural, industrially processed animal leather in order to...

6. Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

DigitalLeather doo

Serbia

Deadline at 31/01/2025

Read more Apply

In-space micro-manufacturing Temperature S...

8. Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Mohit Joshi

UK

Deadline at 31/01/2025

Read more Apply

...ns: Marketing ice

3. Marketing Campaign Of The Future

1. Customer Needs (And Product Properties) Of Tomorrow

2. Finding White Spots In The Product Portfolio

11/2025

Read more Apply

AEPAP: from Advanced Engineering Prototypes to Actual Production

8. Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Orodjarstvo Križaj d.o.o.

Slovenia

Deadline at 30/01/2025

Read more Apply

Young people live sustainably

3. Marketing campaign of the future

Malsch TechnoValuation

Netherlands

Deadline at 30/01/2025

Adapting ethical impact assessment methodology to needs of innovative companies

1. Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Malsch TechnoValuation

Netherlands

Deadline at 30/01/2025

Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)

2. Finding white spots in the product portfolio

EIT Climate-KIC

Netherlands

Deadline at 30/01/2025

Redesign and updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility

4. Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

ENVIT, environmental engineering and technologies Ltd.

EU MEMBER STATES

Figure 14 : Filter of the list of Challenges according to PCAs.
<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/challenges> - 13/05/2024

FOR IMPACT

A Fluidized Bed Riser Adsorption System For Selective Protein Recovery (FBRAS)

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)
 From Luxembourg
 Responsive
 Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Summary Of The Technology

The invention proposes the development and testing of a novel unit operation, intended for the continuous sequestration of valuable bio-products (including proteins) from a complex feedstock. The system can help to integrate the bio-manufacturing scenario by introducing a novel unit operation that is able to simultaneously remove biomass, selectively capture the product of interest, and concentrate such product. Moreover, the proposed technology can operate in continuous mode, therefore helping to intensify downstream operations. The integration and intensification paradigm results in higher.

Details Of The Technology Offer

Companies within the biomanufacturing sector are constantly looking for novel products and to gain a competitive edge on the market by continuously improving on their production processes; this helps to distinguish themselves from their competitors in an ever-increasing competitive landscape.

Manufacturers of industrial, specialty and pharmaceutical proteins are reporting capacity constraints due to improvements in the product levels currently attainable via fermentation.

The invention proposes the development and testing of a novel unit operation, intended for the continuous sequestration of valuable bio-products (including proteins) from a complex feedstock. The system can help to integrate the bio-manufacturing scenario by introducing a novel unit operation that is able to simultaneously remove biomass, selectively capture the product of interest, and concentrate such product. Moreover, the proposed technology can operate in continuous mode, therefore helping to intensify downstream operations. The integration and intensification paradigm results in higher.

Benefits :

The FBRAS technology has the advantage of being placed directly, for example, after fermentation or cell disruption (i.e., in case of intracellular proteins), creating savings in required equipment and manufacturing time, and decreasing contamination and degradation risks. The system incorporates individual contactors (or "columns") for each stage of operation (e.g., product capture and biomass removal, adsorbent washing, product recovery or "elution", and adsorbent regeneration). The design provides more flexibility in adjusting process conditions and less dependency of the various operational steps on each other in comparison to the mechanically sophisticated column arrangements required in periodic counter current chromatography (PCC) or simulated moving bed (SMB) chromatography. The FBRAS technology is positioned towards manufacturers of industrial proteins due to the observed high volumes of production and the increased competition regarding manufacturing costs, where the developed equipment provides advantages over traditional chromatography systems. More specifically, the positioning of the FBRAS technology will focus on applications like the separation of active polypeptides or in the field of "precision fermentation".

Send a request for information to Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

[Sign up to submit a motivation letter](#)

By clicking "Submit motivation letter" you are signing up on Innoget.com and accepting our [Terms of Service and Privacy policy](#)

Learn more about the topics and find team members!

[Join the slack community](#)

Figure 15 : Challenge description page (pre-signup stage)

<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/technology-calls/165/water-and-energy-saving-in-aquatic-s-centres-facilities> 13/05/2024

A detailed registration template (Figures 16 and 17) will be developed in order to facilitate the process for the evaluation of Motivation Letters by the INDUSAC team after the co-creation team will submit their applications and before being sent to the Company for selection.

Sign Up to INDUSAC

Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for industry-academia collaborations

List of study courses:

Name* Family name*

Address:

Citizenship* Gender*

E-mail:

1/2

Figure 16 : Registration template for students and researchers, part 1
<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/request-access-student>. 14/05/2024

Sign Up to INDUSAC

Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for industry-academia collaborations

Study Start: Foreseen Study End:

Name of public university where you study*

Study course*

Country of the university*

Web page of the university

2/2

I confirm that all the data is correct and that I can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners: European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADE), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Figure 17 : Registration template for students and researchers, part 2
<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/request-access-student>. 14/05/2024

Students and researchers get a user profile (Figure 18) upon completion of the registration and confirmation of the Terms and conditions of the platform.

Figure 18 : Students/researchers profile (This page can only be accessed after registration.)
13/05/2024

Upon completion of the registration process students and researchers will be able to enter into the application process and send the Motivation Letters as a co-creation team. They will access the Challenge description page (Figure 19) where they will (1) get access to the community created in Slack for that specific Challenge and/ or (2) initiate the application of the co-creation team with a Motivation Letter.

Innovative Products and Technologies

A Fluidized Bed Riser Adsorption System For Selective Protein Recovery (FBRAS)

[Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology \(LIST\)](#)

From Luxembourg

Responsive

Innovative Products and Technologies

Summary Of The Technology

The invention proposes the development and testing of a novel unit operation, intended for the continuous sequestration of valuable bio-products (including proteins) from a complex feedstock. The system can help to integrate the bio-manufacturing scenario by introducing a novel unit operation that is able to simultaneously remove biomass, selectively capture the product of interest, and concentrate such product. Moreover, the proposed technology can operate in continuous mode, therefore helping to intensify downstream operations. The integration and intensification paradigm results in higher.

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 Send a request for information to Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

Submit motivation letter

By clicking "Submit motivation letter" you are signing up on Innoget.com and accepting our Terms of Service and Privacy policy

 Learn more about the topics and find team members!

Join the slack community

About Technology Offers

Technology Offers on Research Luxembourg are directly posted and managed by its members as well as evaluation of requests for information. Research Luxembourg is the trusted open innovation and science network aimed at directly connect industry needs with professionals online.

Help

Need help requesting additional information or have questions regarding this Technology Offer? [Contact Research Luxembourg support](#)

- FAQs**
- How do I write a winning proposal?
 - Who will evaluate my proposal?
 - How do I protect my intellectual property?
 - Do I have to reveal confidential information?
 - Do I need to sign a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) before submitting my proposal?
 - How long will it take to get a response?
 - What happen if I am elected?
 - What happen if I am not elected?

Figure 19 : Challenge description page containing access to Slack community and Application submission process

<https://www.innoget.com/technology-offers/9743/a-fluidized-bed-riser-adsorption-system-for-selective-protein-recovery-fbras>, 14/05/2024

The application process of the co-creation team's Motivation Letter will guarantee that co-creation teams are formed and applied according to the program and legal requirements set by the INDUSAC methodology. Students/ researchers will be brought to their settings area (Figure 20) to invite their teammates to participate and confirm their applications (Motivation Letter) before being sent to the INDUSAC Evaluation team.

Figure 20 : Students/researchers' settings for teammates' invitation management (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

The platform will set the rules so a popup message will be shown to student/ researcher teams whenever the criteria is not met and only after meeting all the INDUSAC eligibility criteria the co-creation team can proceed with the process of submitting a motivation letter. Figures 21, 22, and 23 show the response to different events in a co-creation team's application submission of their Motivation Letter.

Figure 21 : Reminder to build a Team before you proceed with Motivation Letter (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Figure 22 : Guidance for Missing Requirements (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

You can submit a motivation letter after you have fulfilled all these requirements for your team. ✕

- Requirement #1
- Requirement #2
- Requirement #3
- The team must have at least 3 participants
- The team should consist of at more than 50% shall be woman
- Requirement #6
- Requirement #7

You have fulfilled all the requirements for the team, and now you can send a motivation letter.

[Submit motivation letter](#)

Figure 23 : Necessary criteria to proceed to the Motivation Letter Submission (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Motivation Letters will be submitted by the team leader (Figure 24) according to the predefined requirements and will go to the INDUSAC Evaluation team.

The screenshot shows the submission interface for a challenge titled "Seeking the way of improving the rheological characteristics of soy lecithin". The page includes a search bar, navigation icons (Home, My Activity, My Network, Messages, Notifications, Resources), and a "Submit Motivation" button. Below the challenge title, there is an "Attachments" section with a "Drag & Drop your files here" area. The "Team ID" section contains a text input field with "298173" and a list of team members: Theresa Webb, Savannah Nguyen, Devon Lane, Marvin McKinney, Arlene McCoy, and Floyd Miles. The "Describe your team motivation" section contains a text area with a sample motivation letter. On the right side, there is a "FAQs" section with several questions and answers.

Figure 24 : Motivation Letter submission template for Students/ researchers team (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Students/ researchers team will be able to monitor the status of their application from their application dashboard (Figure 25)

Join Us At TechConnect World In June Where We Connect Top Applied Research And Early-Stage Innovation With End Users And Prospectors.

All (4) | Editing (2) | Sent (0) | Under evaluation (2) | Discarded (0) | Rejected (0)

Show 10 entries Search:

Date posted All types Apply

My Replies			Related Posts		
Stage I	Title of my Reply	Date	Title of the Post	Status	Stage II
motivation letter	ID-6459 - SiOx Barrier Nano-Coating with Atmospheric Plasma on PET Bottles View	2023-05-27 ✓ Sent	Seeking material or technology solutions to allow for significant light weightin... PepsiCo	Accepted	Submit A Solution
motivation letter	ID-6458 - Mineral SiOx Barrier or OP Coatings with Atmospheric Plasma Edit Preview Delete	Draft	Seeking bio-based/biodegradable coating and adhe-sive solutions for flexible PHA ... PepsiCo	Editing	Submit A Solution
Challenge Solution	ID-6462 - SiOx Nano-Coating (200 m) with Atmospheric Plasma View	2023-05-27 ✓ Sent	Seeking Materials and Technologies for Green House Gas Reduction in Packaging PepsiCo	Under Evaluation	Submit A Solution
motivation letter	ID-6461 - Making rET impurities less visible by Atmospheric PlasmaCoating Edit Preview Delete	Draft	Seeking solutions to minimize quality and aesthetic challenges of increased rPE... PepsiCo	Editing	Submit A Solution

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 25 : Students/researchers applications dashboard. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

The INDUSAC Evaluation Board will receive a notification on new applications received and will be able to manage them (preselection) from the evaluation dashboard (Figure 26) and either reject them or send them to the Company for their review.

Management Of Solution Proposals

Platform Platform Innoget Platform

Approvals queue Solutions I manage Sol user manages Sol to be modified Sol rejected Modified Sol

Id	Title solution	Updated at	Sent by	Managed by	Technology Call answered	Actions
No data available in table						

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries

Figure 26 : Evaluation of Motivation Letter dashboard (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

The Company will be able to review and select those that better meet their challenge needs based on the Evaluation Criteria for Motivation as defined in the INDUSAC Methodology. Figures 27 to 29 show the Motivation Letter evaluation process on the Company Challenge management dashboard. The students/ researchers team will be informed at this point about the final decision. Accepted Motivation Letters will enter into the Project Phase. Before the project phase starts, all co-creation team members will fill out the questionnaire, and student members only will also sign the FSTP Declaration.

Figure 27 : Dashboard for the Company to manage Challenges and their Motivation Letter and solutions (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Search_ [Q]

Home My Activity Messages Notifications [Profile] Resources

Frame 543

Go Back to My Posts

The power of microalgae for BHT replacement and sustainable innovations
 Motivation Letter 16 submitted to your technology call: Seeking Natural Antioxidants Coming From Microalgae To Replace BHT In Cosmetics And In Personal Care Products

Previous Motivation Letter Next Motivation Letter

Leslie Alexander [Share]
 Student
 From European Union · Reception Date: 2023-05-27 · Lead Qualification Status: New · Team ID: 298173

✗ Reject Motivation Letter [Chat] Accept & Open the chat [Eye] View the team

Description

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganelle unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient productions of native compounds but also recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

How they will address the following aspects

Excellence

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganelle unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient productions of native compounds but also recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

Impact

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganelle unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient productions of native compounds but also recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

Figure 28 : Company access to Motivation Letter for evaluation. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Figure 29 : Company option to reject Motivation Letter and provide feedback to co-creation teams. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

4. Project Phase

Accepted Motivation Letters mean that the selected co-creation teams will enter into the Project phase with the Company.

Within this co-creation period of time the co-creation team and the Company will have access to a private chat where they will be able to communicate as well as access and download the PCAs resources developed in WP1 to co-create a solution that could meet the Company's challenge needs and expectations ([Figure 30](#)).

Figure 30 : Company and the selected target access to a chat and the PCA resources to co-create a solution. (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Solutions developed by the students/ researchers team will be uploaded through the chat. Solutions will be reviewed by the INDUSAC Evaluation Board and the Company before financial transactions (FSTP) will be made to the student members of the co-creation team (outside the Platform) as part of the Offboarding phase.

The implementation report of the Solution will include (see [Figure 31](#)) :

1) Deliverables (according to a specific PCA) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the challenge.

2) Questionnaire “after” - filled out by each member of the co-creation team

- Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
- Compliance with the ethics requirement which will be submitted via the platform.

Seeking the way of improving the rheological characteristics of soy lecithin

Posted by Anonymous Organization ■ Responsive ■ Specific Technical Innovation ■ Project Size Range : 50.000 - 250.000 € ■ Deadline at 22/12/2023 ■ EMEA

Save draft
Submit Solution

Attachments*

Drag & Drop your files here

Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution.
Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS

Add your team mates here use one field for each member.* How does this field work?

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

@yourself	0/50	@teammate 1	0/50
@teammate 2	0/50	@teammate 3	0/50
@teammate 4	0/50	@teammate 5	0/50

+

Taras, start writing the title of your Challenge*

Identify your motivation letter with a self-explanatory title

¿Qué es Lorem Ipsum?*

Lorem Ipsum es simplemente el texto de relleno de las imprentas y archivos de texto. Lorem Ipsum ha sido el texto de relleno estándar de las industrias desde el año 1500, cuando un impresor (N. del T. persona que se dedica a la imprenta) desconocido usó una galería de textos y los mezcló de tal manera que logró hacer un libro de textos especimen. No sólo sobrevivió 500 años, sino que también ingresó como texto de relleno en documentos electrónicos, quedando esencialmente igual al original. Fue popularizado en los 60s con la creación de las hojas "Letraset", las cuales contenían pasajes de Lorem Ipsum, y más recientemente con software de autoedición, como por ejemplo Aldus PageMaker, el cual incluye versiones de Lorem Ipsum.

86g/1000

¿Qué es Lorem Ipsum?*

Lorem Ipsum es simplemente el texto de relleno de las imprentas y archivos de texto. Lorem Ipsum ha sido el texto de relleno estándar de las industrias desde el año 1500, cuando un impresor (N. del T. persona que se dedica a la imprenta) desconocido usó una galería de textos y los mezcló de tal manera que logró hacer un libro de textos especimen. No sólo sobrevivió 500 años, sino que también ingresó como texto de relleno en documentos electrónicos, quedando esencialmente igual al original. Fue popularizado en los 60s con la creación de las hojas "Letraset", las cuales contenían pasajes de Lorem Ipsum, y más recientemente con software de autoedición, como por ejemplo Aldus PageMaker, el cual incluye versiones de Lorem Ipsum.

86g/1000

Library of Resources

- [Document 1](#)
- [Document 2](#)
- [Document 3](#)

About you

Your complete profile will be included with your solution proposal. Review your information below.

Taras Zaiachuk
UI/UX Designer · Ukraine

Expert in Electronics, IT and Telecomms. Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies. Industrial Technologies and 22 more [+Add more](#)

Email address: moneytv13@gmail.com

Phone number: [Add phone number](#) [Show phone number](#)

Innoget profile: <https://www.innoget.com/Users/taraz-zaiachuk>

Your complete profile will be included with your application. [Update your profile](#)

Technology Calls on Innoget are directly posted and managed by its members as well as evaluation of proposals. Innoget is the trusted open innovation and science network aimed at directly connect industry needs with professionals online.

FAQs

- [How do I protect my Intellectual Property?*](#)
- [Do I have to reveal Confidential Information?*](#)
- [Do I need to sign a non-disclosure \(NDA\) before submitting my proposal?*](#)
- [Who will evaluate my proposal?*](#)
- [How long will it take before getting a response?*](#)
- [What happen if I am elected?*](#)
- [What happen if I am not elected?*](#)
- [How do I write a winning proposal? See the Tips in the Description section](#)

Figure 31 : Solution implementation report submission template (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

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WWW.INDUSAC.EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297.

The Company (Deliverable quality) and INDUSAC (Technical performance indicators, Business performance indicators, Deadline Compliance) will be able to evaluate (Figure 32) the solutions and either accept or reject them as shown in Figures 33 and Figure 34)

Motivation Letter Details (Evaluate Button Active)

Search...

Home My Activity My Network Messages Notifications Resources

Go Back to My Posts

The power of microalgae for BHT replacement and sustainable innovations
 Motivation Letter 16 submitted to your technology call: Seeking Natural Antioxidants Coming From Microalgae To Replace BHT In Cosmetics And In Personal Care Products

Previous Motivation Letter Next Motivation Letter

Leslie Alexander · leslie.alexanders@gmail.com
 Scientist
 From European Union · Reception Date: 2023-05-27 · Lead Qualification Status: **New**

Send a message View Leslie's Profile Evaluate this Motivation Letter

Description

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganette unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient productions of native compounds but also recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

Stage of development

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganette unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient productions of native compounds but also recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

Figure 32 : Evaluation of solutions by the Company and INDUSAC (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

Figure 33 : Rejected Solutions (This page can only be accessed after registration.)
14/05/2024

Figure 34 : Awarded Solutions by the Company and INDUSAC (This page can only be accessed after registration.) 14/05/2024

5. Offboarding Phase

The platform will provide information about Challenges and solutions status for the INDUSAC co-creation teams to be able to monitor and manage (Figure 35) the subsequent stages (Legal and Finance) as well as gather feedback from all parties involved.

The dashboard interface includes a top navigation bar with icons for Home, My Activity, My Network, Messages, Notifications, Management, and Resources. A search bar is located on the left side of the top bar. The left sidebar menu is organized into sections: ADMIN (INDUSAC, Administrated By Jordi Rafols, Created 4 September, 2022), PLATFORM SETTINGS (Platform Details, Platform Administration, Platform Analytics), COMMUNITY MANAGEMENT, and CONTENT MANAGEMENT. The main content area is titled "Management Of Solution Proposals" and features a filter bar with tabs for Approvals queue, Solutions I manage, Sol. user manages, Sol. to be modified, Sol. rejected, and Modified Sol. Below the filter bar is a table with the following columns: Id, Title solution, Rejected on, Sent by, Managed by, Technology Call answered, Actions, and Status. The table currently shows "No data available in table" and "Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries".

Figure 35 : INDUSAC co-creation team Challenge and solution management dashboard

III. LIST OF REFERENCES

- <https://indusac.eu/> 13.05.2024
- <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/challenges>. 13.05.2024
- <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/request-access> 13.05.2024
- <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/technology-calls/165/water-and-energy-saving-in-aquatics-centres-facilities> 13.05.2024
- <https://www.innoget.com/technology-offers/9743/a-fluidized-bed-riser-adsorption-system-for-selective-protein-recovery-fbras>. 14.05.2024

IV. ANNEXES

The PCAs below include comprehensive details to facilitate a clear understanding of each Challenge. PCA1 focuses on understanding customer needs and future product properties, while PCA2 aims at identifying gaps in the product portfolio. PCA3 is dedicated to developing future marketing campaigns, and PCA4 involves creating a digital platform based on market analysis. Other PCAs address areas such as e-commerce and digital services (PCA5 and PCA6), business planning (PCA7), innovative product ideas to solve customer pain points (PCA8), and adding services to products to build a product-service system (PCA9). Each PCA provides the title, a detailed problem description with key term explanations, expectations for solutions and impact, the desired profile of the co-creation team, and a formal submission agreement. This structured approach ensures that all Challenges are clearly defined and ready for public posting while maintaining confidentiality where necessary through Non-Disclosure Agreements.

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ANNEX 2: PCA2 Finding white spot in the product portfolio	43
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ANNEX 8: PCA8 Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain	57
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ANNEX 1: PCA1 Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Home
My Activity
My Network
Messages
Notifications
Resources

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario/Trend analysis and references (e.g., Word)
- Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g., Excel)

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2.)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Minimum 300 characters

Publish

Save Draft

Manage posts

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Input:

Do you have scenarios/already known trends available to give to students?

Minimum 150 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Minimum 300 characters

Link to Slack-Channel:**Select challenge manager**

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

Click to select a challenge manager among your company account subusers

INDUSAC Submission agreement

Users who want to submit a proposal to your challenge will carefully read the terms of the agreement and will send the form only if they agree and accept the conditions you include in the INDUSAC Submission Agreement. Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set in order to specify the cooperation. Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC submission agreement. If there is a conflict, INDUSAC submission agreement prevails.

[View the Submission Agreement provided by INDUSAC](#)

I agree to use this submission agreement Create my own submission agreement

Privacy settings for this challenge

Post as Taras Zalachuk from Company Post as Company

ANNEX 2: PCA2 Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Q

Home
My Activity
My Network
Messages
Notifications
Resources

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS

The development of new business models for a given product.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Strategic analysis of product portfolio (e.g., BCG-matrix)
- Clustering of product portfolio (e.g., PowerPoint)
- Action-plan / white spot analysis for relevant clusters

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2.)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Publish

Save Draft

👤 👤 Manage posts

42

WWW.INDUSAC.EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297.

Context:

Use Cases – In which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Type in a search term

- Aerospace
- Agriculture and Marine Resources
- Agrofood Industry
- Biological Sciences
- Communications
- Computer related
- Consumer related
- Digitalization
- Electronics Related Market
- Electronics, IT and Telecomms
- Energy Market
- Energy Technology
- Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology
- Industrial Products
- Industrial Technologies
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies
- Lightweight
- Measurements and Standards
- Medical Health related
- Ophthalmology
- Other
- Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences
- Protecting Man and Environment
- Social and Economics concerns
- Sustainability

Input:

Do you have a presentation of your product portfolio which you can share with the team? Do you have future product ideas which the team should consider?

Write your answer

Minimum 150 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Would you like the students to explore a specific direction or market? Do you have any white spots already identified that do not have to be included in the analysis? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Additional information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g. Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

Click to select a challenge manager among your company account subusers

INDUSAC Submission agreement

Users who want to submit a proposal to your challenge will carefully read the terms of the agreement and will send the form only if they agree and accept the conditions you include in the INDUSAC Submission Agreement. Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set in order to specify the cooperation. Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC submission agreement. If there is a conflict, INDUSAC submission agreement prevails.

[View the Submission Agreement provided by INDUSAC](#)

I agree to use this submission agreement Create my own submission agreement

Privacy settings for this challenge

Post as Taras Zaiachuk from Company Post as Company

ANNEX 3: PCA3 Marketing campaign of the future

Home
My Activity
My Network
Messages
Notifications
Resources

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

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Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Publish

Save Draft

👤
👤
👤 Manage posts

Marketing campaign of the future

Design of a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis with focus on customers
- Trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends
- Design of a marketing campaign

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2.)

Title for your Challenge:

Enter a title for your challenge

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Describe your challenge briefly

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

- Aerospace
- Agriculture and Marine Resources
- Agrofood Industry
- Biological Sciences
- Communications
- Computer related
- Consumer related
- Digitalization
- Electronics Related Market
- Electronics, IT and Telecomms
- Energy Market
- Energy Technology
- Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology
- Industrial Products
- Industrial Technologies
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies
- Lightweight
- Measurements and Standards
- Medical Health related
- Ophthalmology
- Other
- Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences
- Protecting Man and Environment
- Social and Economics concerns
- Sustainability

Input:

Do you have already known trends available to give to students for further development? Do you have an existing marketing campaign which was a success or which clearly did not deliver the results you expected?

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the marketing campaign to evolve? Would you like the students to explore a specific direction or market? Do you have any discarded solutions already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this challenge/ Marketing Campaigns you consider to be best practice examples/ Trends you may have already identified/ Details about your customer groups).

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

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ANNEX 4: PCA4 Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

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Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a **digital platform prototype** based on a **market analysis**.

Long description of PCA - more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis to define platform
- Digital Platform prototype (click dummy) (based on existing Product profiles)

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2.)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Context:

Use Cases - In which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Type in a search term

Input:

Which digital platforms are relevant as references? Do you have a website/ another type of online sales channel that should be used as a reference? Do you have prior market research results you want to make available to the student teams?

Write your answer

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the digital platform to evolve? Would you like the students to use a specific platform tool? Do you have any discarded solutions already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Platforms that can be used as reference/ Tools you can supply the students with).

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

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ANNEX 5: PCA5 E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)

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Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- **Persona**
- **Product Profile**
- **Service/ Product idea**

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2..)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Publish

Save Draft

Manage posts

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Type in a search term

- Aerospace • Agriculture and Marine Resources • Agrofood Industry • Biological Sciences • Communications •
- Computer related • Consumer related • Digitalization • Electronics Related Market • Electronics, IT and Telecomms •
- Energy Market • Energy Technology • Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology • Industrial Products • Industrial Technologies •
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies • Lightweight • Measurements and Standards • Medical Health related •
- Ophthalmology • Other • Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences • Protecting Man and Environment • Social and Economics concerns •
- Sustainability •

Input:

Are there existing target groups which you have already identified and want the personas to focus on? Do you have additional information you want to supply the teams with?

Write your answer

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Would you like the students to target a specific customer group? Do you have any discarded product or service ideas already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

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ANNEX 6: PCA6 E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)

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Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Publish

Save Draft

👤 👤 👤 **Manage posts**

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of Increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario map
- Catalogue of future robust product properties
- Product profile/ Product ideas

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2...)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

- Aerospace
- Agriculture and Marine Resources
- Agrofood Industry
- Biological Sciences
- Communications
- Computer related
- Consumer related
- Digitalization
- Electronics Related Market
- Electronics, IT and Telecomms
- Energy Market
- Energy Technology
- Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology
- Industrial Products
- Industrial Technologies
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies
- Lightweight
- Measurements and Standards
- Medical Health related
- Ophthalmology
- Other
- Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences
- Protecting Man and Environment
- Social and Economics concerns
- Sustainability

Input:

If you have identified scenarios already, please provide them to the teams. The challenge can be solved based on scenarios you give as input or on trends the teams identify and analyse. Please clarify which option you want the teams to use.

Minimum 180 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Do you have any discarded solutions already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Trends or Megatrends relevant for your sector).

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

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INDUSAC Submission agreement

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ANNEX 7: PCA7 Business plan - reduce your risk and optimize your planning

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Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Publish

Save Draft

Manage posts

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning

The development of a [business plan](#) after a [SWOT analysis](#) and an estimation of profitability.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- SWOT-Analysis
- Business plan
- Estimation of profitability

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2...)

Title for your Challenge:

Enter a title for your challenge

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Describe your challenge briefly

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

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Input:

Do you have former business plans that you want the teams to use as input? Do you prefer specific tools you can supply the teams with for the estimation of profitability?

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Do you want the teams to focus on a specific business unit? Do you have any discarded solutions already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

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ANNEX 8: PCA8 Innovative product ideas that solve the customer plan

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Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Publish

Save Draft

👤 👤 Manage posts

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Development of alternative product ideas
- Utility analysis and evaluation of ideas
- Virtual prototype

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2...)

Title for your Challenge:

Enter a title for your challenge

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Describe your challenge briefly

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Context:

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

- Aerospace
- Agriculture and Marine Resources
- Agrofood Industry
- Biological Sciences
- Communications
- Computer related
- Consumer related
- Digitalization
- Electronics Related Market
- Electronics, IT and Telecomms
- Energy Market
- Energy Technology
- Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology
- Industrial Products
- Industrial Technologies
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies
- Lightweight
- Measurements and Standards
- Medical Health related
- Ophthalmology
- Other
- Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences
- Protecting Man and Environment
- Social and Economics concerns
- Sustainability

Input:

This challenge works based on a customer need you have already identified. Please specify the need here. You may give all additional information about the need/ your customers/ your target group here.

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Would you like the students to target a specific customer group where you identified the need? Do you have any discarded product ideas already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: virtual prototypes you have developed in the past).

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

Click to select a challenge manager among your company account subusers

INDUSAC Submission agreement

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Privacy settings for this challenge

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ANNEX 9: PCA9 Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS

Home My Activity My Network Messages Notifications Resources

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

<input type="radio"/> Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow <small>Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.</small>	<input type="radio"/> Finding white spots in the product portfolio <small>Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements.</small>
<input type="radio"/> Marketing campaign of the future <small>Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.</small>	<input type="radio"/> Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis <small>Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.</small>
<input type="radio"/> E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Persona) <small>Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.</small>	<input type="radio"/> E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios) <small>Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.</small>
<input type="radio"/> Business plan – reduce your risk and optimize your planning <small>The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.</small>	<input type="radio"/> Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain <small>Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.</small>
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS <small>The development of new business models for a given product.</small>	

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Long description of PCA – more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona (user behaviour)
- Business model
- 3 alternatives and subsequent utility analysis

Project process description (kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting) Illustrated as Gantt-Chart (Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2...)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Upload a picture to represent your Challenge

Drag & Drop your files here

Possible formats: PNG, JPG

Short description:

Minimum 140 characters

Initial Problem description:

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Minimum 300 characters

Publish

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Context:

Use Cases – In which context does this problem/ challenge appear. What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview about the problem context.

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Connection to Cross-cutting areas:

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and digitalisation

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Categorization

Giving a good categorization is key for your challenge to be found by appropriate experts

Type in a search term

- Aerospace • Agriculture and Marine Resources • Agrofood Industry • Biological Sciences • Communications •
- Computer related • Consumer related • Digitalization • Electronics Related Market • Electronics, IT and Telecomms •
- Energy Market • Energy Technology • Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology • Industrial Products • Industrial Technologies •
- Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies • Lightweight • Measurements and Standards • Medical Health related •
- Ophthalmology • Other • Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences • Protecting Man and Environment • Social and Economics concerns •
- Sustainability •

Input:

Please use this field to give all the details needed about the product you want the teams to focus on. Exchange of files will be possible as soon as teams are selected to solve your challenge.

Write your answer

Minimum 160 characters

Expectations:

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve? Do you have any discarded business models already? What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver? Display of the business models within a business model canvas?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Desired team profile:

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Additional Information:

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this challenge/ Information about the main rival product).

Write your answer

Minimum 300 characters

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your subusers to manage this Challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members

Click to select a challenge manager among your company account subusers

INDUSAC Submission agreement

Users who want to submit a proposal to your challenge will carefully read the terms of the agreement and will send the form only if they agree and accept the conditions you include in the INDUSAC Submission Agreement. Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set in order to specify the cooperation. Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC submission agreement. If there is a conflict, INDUSAC submission agreement prevails.

[View the Submission Agreement provided by INDUSAC](#)

I agree to use this submission agreement Create my own submission agreement

Privacy settings for this challenge

Post as Taras Zaiachuk from Company Post as Company

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